

Education for Self-Reliance, Life Skill Education and its Significance in African Traditional Education

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Abstract

The paper examines Education for self-reliance and its significance in African Traditional Education. The paper adopted analytical method because several articles, journals and literatures related education for self-reliance and its significance in African Traditional Education were reviewed. Education for self-reliance is about gaining self-independence, responsibility and democratic involvement, while life skills help to promote critical thinking, problem solving, effective communication skill, decision-making, interpersonal relationship skills, self-awareness, self-esteem and self-confidence. African traditional education emphasizes social responsibility, job orientation, political participation, moral values, attitudes, skills and other forms of behaviours which are of positive values to the society. The paper suggested, Education must be problem solving and work oriented. A national sensitization campaign should create awareness on the importance of vocational education and self-reliance of the citizens. Also, Self-reliance and life skill education should be incorporated in the curriculum of all level of education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, Education for Self-Reliance (ESR), Life Skill Education, Education Systems in Africa.

Introduction

Education is the development of individuals according to the needs and the demands of the society. Education is a stabilizer of the society, a conservator of culture, norms, values and traditions. It is also important to note that the main purpose of education is to train individuals to meet the needs of the society and find better ways to boost the national development in the best possible ways. It is an instrument for change and social transformations. Nwafor (2016) acknowledge that education is the aggregate processes by which a child or young adult develops the abilities, attitudes, skills and other forms of behaviours which are of positive values to the society in which they live. Education could also be defined as the process of cultural transmission and renewal, that is a process whereby the adult members of a society carefully guide the development of infants and young children, initiating them into the culture of the society.

Self-reliance education could be viewed as the development of knowledge, power, as well as the feeling of responsibility in an individual. Its freedom and independence of the self, self-emancipation and self-realization. It is an education that encourages creative thinking as well as practical creative transformation (Njoh, 2012). The concept of self-reliance is all about self-confidence, responsibility and democratic involvement. It means delivering knowledge about self-reliance. It is system of education that equips learners with knowledge, skills and attitudes for tackling societal problems. It is an education that prepare the youth for work in predominantly agricultural society; enable learners appreciate and develop a culture of African that preserves the national tradition, individual responsibility, tolerance and respect.

(Anobi, 2017). Moreover, Anyanwu (2004) contributed that education for self-reliance is aimed at creating in each citizen an inquiring mind; ability to learn from others; basic confidence in one's own position and ability to learn and contribute to the society. Self-reliance is the ability to think, act without the help or influence of others and the ability to decide what to do for the societ. Self-reliance is one of the bases of effective community development in Africa. Self reliance is located centrally within the discourse of community development and related to concepts like self-help, mutual-help, indigenous participation and rural development. It advocates the need for people to improve their condition using local initiatives and resources in their own hands. Its widespread acceptance in the development planning of most African countries has the tendency to give greater stimulus and cohesiveness to community development in these countries. He recorded that in most African countries, community development has depended significantly on voluntary cooperative efforts. This follows a traditional trait that clearly underscores the virtue of self-reliance.

The emphasis is to involve groups of people in planned programmes from which they may gain skills that will enable them to cope more successfully with the problems of their everyday life

(Mosha, 2016). Nevertheless, Charle and Lotsmart (2015) noted that self-reliance is a state of mind that regards one's own mental and material resources as the primary stock to draw on the pursuit of one's objectives and findings of emotion. Self-reliance in community development demands that community members should apply their knowledge and skills to the resources at their disposal. They added that the development of related skills and attitudes of a people can enable them to satisfy their basic needs, to grow self-reliant and to minimize precarious dependence on the development of the communities. It encourages the need for people to improve their living conditions using home initiatives and resources at their disposal.

However, Life skills education differs in its objectives and contents from country to country and from one locality to another. Life skills could be seen as abilities for adapting positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. Life skills are essentially those abilities which help to promote mental well-being and competence in young people as they face the realities of life. It enables children to learn and practice skills, which is child-centred and activity oriented activities. Life skills education is based on the philosophy that young people should be empowered to take more responsibility for their actions (Avci et al., 2021). life skill education strengthens the ability of an individual to meet the needs and demands of the present society. and helps in dealing with the above issues in a manner to get desired behavior practical. Imparting life skill training through inculcating life skill education will help youth to overcome such difficulties in life. life skill education become important as it is associated with African traditional education. African traditional education can generally be defined as the form of learning in African traditional societies in which knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the tribe, were passed from father's or elders to children, by means of oral instructions and practical activities.

Through life skills education, young generations are equipped with foundational skills necessary for transitioning into productive adulthood; learn to deal with difficult emotions; improve self-esteem; feel empathy; learn to listen to others carefully; learn to set personal boundary; handle dispute well; find balance between priorities and demands; communicate confidently; set goals; make decisions; solve problems; think critically and creatively; use executive functional skills; and learn to bounce back from adversity. Life skill is associated with concrete ways of thinking and executing tasks so that youths will make effective decisions, set relevant goals. Life skills approaches facilitate skills learning and promote social and environmental support that aim to influence health and social behaviour in a positive way. Life skills education is based on the teaching of this generic type of skills for life and it includes the practice of life skills in relation to major health and social needs. In this type of education, children and adolescents are actively involved in a dynamic teaching and learning process that is often based on the principles of social learning theory. The methods used include working in groups, brainstorming, role play, games and

debates. The pedagogy of life skills education is therefore based on cooperative learning, participative activities and experiential learning. Life skills are essentially those abilities that help to promote mental well-being and competence in young people as they face the realities of life. They can be utilized in many content areas, thus: prevention of drug use, sexual violence, teenage pregnancy, HIV/AIDS prevention and suicide prevention. The definition extends into business education, environmental education, peace education or education for development, livelihood and income generation, among others. In short, life skills empower young people to take positive action to protect themselves and promote health and positive social relationships (Prajapati et al, 2017)

Traditional education has been with the Africans since the inception of the black man right from the neophytic age. Every society whether white or black has its own system of training and ways of educating her citizen. Lim (2019) noted that every society whether simple or complex has its own system of training and educating its youth, and education for good life has been one of the most persistent concern of men through history. The traditional education system in Africa is as old as the people, this education starts from birth and its aim was the transmission of culture from one generation to another. No wonder Osokoya (2010) recorded that traditional education is a process of transmitting the accumulated intellectual skills, values, beliefs and attitudes of the society from one generation to another.

Rogoff (2014) contributed that the education has helped to prepare youth for active participation and transmission of her rich cultural values from one generation to another. The history of impacting knowledge into the younger generation in Nigeria is as old as humans in the society. Citizens have been transferring knowledge, skills, values, norms, belief and the acceptable attitude to their younger generations long before the advent of the Europeans. Although, skills, values and knowledge transmitted during the period were not written anywhere but they were carefully engraved in the hearts of every citizen and the generations that received the education became a lot better under the system. The society cared greatly for their next generation and the people lived collectively in peace and harmony.

Nevertheless, before the introduction of colonial system of government, all the ethnic groups in Nigeria such as, Yoruba, Hausa, and Igbo had their own traditional citizenship education, social values, legal and civic right and duties which they taught and expected their people to follow in their day-to-day activities. All these values, rights, duties and obligations were passed orally from one generation to another as part of their cultures, but with the coming of the Europeans the culture and value became less emphasized because the African indigenous culture was tagged barbaric and uncivilized (Taiwo, 2009).

The introduction of reading and writing which started with the coming of the Europeans in 1842 shifted attention from the traditional values of hard work, discipline, honesty, truth, responsibility, self-reliance, commitment, respect for lives and properties to the classrooms where reading, writing and memorization were done without recourse to the traditional values, this led to value disintegration where citizens no longer cared for one another. The traditional values and education became less important and citizens became less concerned about the well-being of each other (Adeyinka & Babarinde, 2011).

Increasingly, there has been a global shift towards recognizing and understanding African traditional education as a viable and legitimate form of education. A growing body of scientific literature has described indigenous ways of learning, in different cultures. Learning in indigenous communities is a process that involves all members in the community. The learning styles that children use in their indigenous schooling are the same ones that occur in their community context. These indigenous learning styles often include: observation, imitation, use of narrative/storytelling, collaboration, and cooperation as seen among African communities (McCarty, 2014). The child feels that he/she is a vital member of the community and encouraged to participate in a meaningful way by community members. Children often effectively learn skills through this system, without being taught explicitly or in a formal manner. This differs from Western learning styles, which tend to include methods such as explicit instruction in which a figure of authority directs the learner's attention, and testing. Creating an educational environment for indigenous children allows for a child to retain knowledge more easily, because they are learning in a way that was encouraged from infancy within their family and community (Ezeife, 2012).

Education for Self-Reliance (ESR)

The concept of self-reliance is all about self-confidence, responsibility and democratic involvement. It means delivering knowledge about self-reliance. It is a system of education that equips learners with knowledge, skills and attitudes for tackling societal problems. It is an education that prepares the youth for work in predominantly agricultural society; enable learners appreciate and develop a culture of Africa that preserves the national tradition, individual responsibility, tolerance and respect. (Anobi, 2017)

This concept is being given great attention and considered as a new blueprint for community development. Self-reliance is the social and economic ability of an individual, a household or a community to meet essential needs (including protection, food, water, shelter, personal safety, health and education) in a sustainable manner and with dignity (Arthman et al., 2018)

Twalo (2019) also reported that self-reliance, as a programme approach, refers to developing and strengthening livelihoods of persons and reducing their vulnerability and long-term reliance on humanitarian/external assistance. Self-reliance will build upon strong social structures and increasing levels of economic activity, social and economic links with local communities. However, African traditional education is built on self-reliance and life skill education

Life Skill Education

Life skills could be seen as a group of psychosocial competencies and interpersonal skills that help people take positive decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationships, empathize with others, cope with others and manage their lives in a healthy and productive manner. It may be directed toward personal actions or toward others, as well as toward actions to change the surrounding environment to make it conducive for health (Cassidy, et al 2018).

Benhardt et al. (2014) contributed that life skills are work skills in addition to skills to be academically oriented. It is an effort to improve knowledge, attitude and skills that enable learners to live independently. Life skills-oriented education is a program which is capable of improving knowledge and skills possessed, to improve the quality of life and help others who need it. Zelyvurt et al. (2018) stated that life skills constitute a continuum of knowledge and aptitude that are necessary for a person to function affectively in the society. Life skills education are programmes that can provide skills that are practical, related to the needs of the jobs, and potential economy or industry in the community (Teane, 2021). This activity mirrors the various capacities a person needs to pursue his life successfully, happily and with dignity in society. It is also stated that life skills education is organized to provide learning opportunities to gain knowledge, skills and grow the creativity, innovation, responsibility, and encouragement to bear the risk of entrepreneurship to improve the quality of life (Bharath & Kishore, 2018). Everyone in the society needs life skills education to improve the quality of life. Therefore, both education for self-reliance and life skills education are needed for personal growth and community development.

The Basic life skills curriculum offers youth the emotional, social and intellectual tools needed to achieve success in life within the community and work places. It provides youth with new knowledge and the opportunity to apply novel skills in a safe environment for the successful transitioning to the adulthood. Life skills provide readily available tools to deal with challenges of daily lives the youth face, from managing their emotions to make an informed decision. It also helps to develop children's personality, talents and mental, physical abilities to realize true potential through learning and make effective decisions to live harmonically together in the society. The Education for All (2000) included life skills among the essential learning tool for survival,

capacity development and quality life. It also documented that all young people and adults have the human right to benefit from an education that includes learning to know, to do, to live together, recognizing the importance of living together as much as acquiring knowledge from an academic environment (Tran et al., 2021).

UNESCO (2008) cited in Kadenyi and Kariu (2011) listed the ten core life skill strategies and techniques as: problem solving, critical thinking, effective communication skills, decision-making, creative thinking, interpersonal relationship skills, self-awareness building skills, empathy, coping with stress and emotions. Self-awareness, self-esteem and self-confidence are essential tools for understanding one's strengths and weaknesses. Consequently, the individual is able to discern available opportunities and prepare to face possible threats. This leads to the development of a social awareness of the concerns of one's family and society. Subsequently, it is possible to identify problems that arise within both the family and society.

They identified the following criteria to ensure a successful life skills base education as follows:

- 1.It should not only address knowledge and attitude change, but, more importantly, behaviour change.
- 2.Traditional "information-based" approaches are generally not sufficient to yield changes in attitudes and behaviours. For example, a lecture on "safe behaviour" will not necessarily lead to the practice of safe behaviour. Therefore, the lecture should be substantiated with exercises and situations where participants can practice safe behaviour and experience its effects. The adult learning theory emphasizes that adults learn best when the study is associated with experience and practice.
- 3.It will work best when augmented or reinforced. If a message is given once, the brain remembers only 10% of it one day later, and when the same message is given six times a day, the brain remembers 90% of it. Hence the need to repeat, recaps, reinforces and reviews.
- 4.It will work best if combined with policy development, access to appropriate health services, community development and media.

Furthermore, self-reliance education and life skill education have a positive influence on African traditional education.

African Traditional Education

Mushi (2009) acknowledged that African education is a process of passing among the tribal members and from one generation to another the inherited knowledge, skills, cultural traditions, norms and values of the people. Enyi (2011) reported that African traditional education emphasizes social responsibility, job orientation, political participation, spiritual and moral values. Therefore, traditional education has relationship with self-reliance education and life skill education. African traditional education is a lifelong education and also functionalism was the main guiding principle. Functionalism refers to practical-oriented, felt-need education that is aimed at identifying and providing solutions for societal needs as well as empowerment of the educated.

Fafunwa (1991) stated that Children and Youth learnt by participatory education through demonstration, recitation, ritual ceremony and imitation. In traditional African education, the method of teaching was practically oriented. The subjects are for instance wrestling, dancing, drumming, racing, local history, proverbs, riddles and storytelling. The traditional system of education was integrated in such a way that unemployment was minimal. Garcia (2013) stated that the indigenous education in Kenya, Nigeria and other African countries brought about skill acquisition and apprenticeship training system as a part of wider education process in which the African indigenous societies passed on their cultural heritage from one generation to the next.

Omola (2021) reported that African traditional education involved practical such as farming, fishing, cooking, carving, knitting and so on. Recreation subjects includes writing, dancing, drumming, acrobatic display, racing, while intellectual training included the study of local history, environment (Local geography, plants and animals), poetry, reasoning, riddles, proverbs, storytelling and story relays. It combined physical training with character molding and manual activities with intellectual training. This type of education relies heavily on education for self-reliance and life skill education. The African child likes to explore his immediate environment; observes adults in their activities, and imitate them – he enjoys discovering new situations. Here there is no cultural difference between the African, the European or the Asiatic child, but the modus operandi may vary in terms of method and equipment. In traditional African society the child intuitively jumps, climbs a tree, dances or performs a balancing act because his siblings or his elders do the same. (May & Aikman, 2017)

Doige (2013) collaborated that traditional African education can be said to encourage intellectual growth and development. Observation, imitation and participation are some of the major learning processes even in this modern age. The African child learns the local geography and history of his community. He is very familiar with the hills and valleys, the fertile and the non-fertile areas; he knows the rainy season and when to expect a dry spell; he knows the time of the hunting and

fishing seasons. Local history is taught by the elders in each household and the songs of praise which accompany many of the historical events make the oral traditional history a stimulating experience which is hard to forget

Skills like masonry, carpentry, clay working, carving, cloth making, building and construction, were taught in the view of maintaining the socio-economic and cultural heritage of the society. Moreover, the learners/recipients acquire communal attitudes rather than individual. From communalism philosophical base point of view, students were taught to respect the culture of the whole society, and they used their acquired knowledge for service of the society. Hence, Self-reliance education and life skill education has an important role in African traditional education. The aim of traditional African education is multilateral and the objective is to produce an individual who is honest, respectable, skilled, co-operative and conforms to the social order of the day. Although the educational objectives cannot be neatly distinguished, according to Nwafor (2016) seven aspects can be identified:

- 1.To develop the child's latent physical skill.
- 2.To develop character.
- 3.To indicate respect for elders and those in position of authority.
- 4.To develop intellectual skills
- 5.To acquire specific vocational training and to develop a healthy attitude towards honest labour.
- 6.To develop a sense of belonging and to participate actively in family and community affairs.
- 7.To develop, appreciate and promote the cultural heritage of the community at large. Suffice it then to say that this education was aimed at training a child physically, developing his character, intellectual training, vocational training and respect for the elders and peers.

African traditional education can achieve its aim through self-reliance and life skill education as it encourages creative thinking as well as practical creative transformation activity. All forms of traditional education aimed at inculcating respect for others, recognition of equality of all human being; and combating all forms of discrimination (racism, gender-biased, religion etc.) by fostering a spirit of tolerance and peace among human beings (Lim, 2019)). Traditional education is associated with knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to equip and re-orientate people in order to function or participate effectively in all activities aimed at the collective goals or development of society, nation or country.

The Significance of African Traditional Education

African traditional education is known for its holistic nature, emphasizing the development of moral, physical, and intellectual faculties. Before the advent of Western education, African societies placed a premium on self-reliance and life skills as part of a well-rounded upbringing. Adeyemi and Akindele (2019), traditional African education was centered on preparing individuals for adult roles within their communities, with a strong focus on practical, moral, and social responsibilities.

The integration of traditional life skills education into modern schooling systems is discussed by Mutua and Wanjohi (2022), who examine how indigenous African knowledge systems and traditional apprenticeship programs continue to influence current vocational education models in Sub-Saharan Africa. This underscores the enduring value of African traditional education in cultivating a sense of community, responsibility, and sustainability.

Furthermore, Dada and Owolabi (2023) examine the relevance of traditional African education in the post-colonial African landscape. They suggest that while African societies have adopted Western educational systems, there remains an important role for integrating indigenous educational practices into formal curricula. In this view, education for self-reliance and life skills education are not new concepts but rather a modern articulation of practices deeply rooted in African tradition.

Conclusion

Education is viewed as an important tool to improve the situation of people by pursuing economic, social and cultural development; it provides the people with individual empowerment and self-determination. Life skills help to promote critical thinking, problem solving, effective communication skills, decision-making, creative thinking, interpersonal relationship skills, self-awareness building skills, empathy, and coping with stress and emotions. Education for self-reliance and life skills education has evolved from Africa's traditional educational systems and continues to be vital in preparing individuals for the demands of modern society. African traditional education has always emphasized these values through practical learning, social cooperation, and self-sufficiency. Modern education systems in Africa, while influenced by Western models, are increasingly recognizing the value of integrating indigenous educational practices to foster resilience, adaptability, and economic empowerment. Future educational reforms in Africa should aim to incorporate both modern life skills and the self-reliance principles from traditional education to promote sustainable development.

Suggestions

1. A national sensitization campaign to create awareness on the importance of vocational education should be undertaken to ensure self-reliance.
2. More vocational schools should be established for life skills and self-reliance programmes
3. The school curriculum should reflect traditions and cultures of the societies.
4. Self-reliance and life skill education should be incorporated in the curriculum of all level of education in Nigeria.
5. Integrating vocational training and entrepreneurship skills within basic education will prepare students for diverse economic roles.

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